

THE ROLE OF ICT IN IMPROVING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF THE LESSON IN ELEMENTARY GRADES

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Annotation: today, the effective use of modern technologies of computer and information technology in improving the quality and effectiveness of primary education is considered the main factor. The effective use of ICT in teaching school subjects in the education system in our country is an urgent issue. It is information technology that is considered a universal means of Education, allowing not only to form knowledge, skills and abilities in students, but also to develop personal characteristics, satisfy their interest in cognition.

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Today, Information Technology is developing on a large scale all over the world. Obviously, it is necessary to establish the targeted use of new information technologies in the educational process. Modern society is characterized by the active use of the world Information Network, which is not limited in terms of the volume and speed of information transmission. The emergence and widespread spread of multimedia and Internet technologies makes it possible to use ICT as a means of communication, upbringing, penetration into the world community.

Today, like all areas, it is difficult to imagine the educational process without computer and Information Technology. And this does not mean that the use of the capabilities of computer and information technology solves the solution of all issues, that is, the correction and processing of information-this guarantees the full formation of knowledge, skills and abilities, since all this is considered only one of the effective additional means of teaching.

Nowadays, especially since such high requirements are imposed on primary education that the implementation of these, incessantly improving the methods and techniques used, requires research and creativity. The main theme of today is that we must work hard so that the future young generation can become educated, wise and mature.

As the famous scientist Craig Barrett said: 'The Miracle is created by teachers, not computers.' No matter how fully the school is endowed with the most modern means

of information and communication, all efforts are ineffective if the pedagogues cannot put them into practice.

Of great importance in the teaching of elementary school students is the equipment and effective use of classes with guidance weapons. The use of various effective methods in teaching, research to improve the quality of the lesson, especially improving the skills of the correct and productive use of electronic textbooks, are decisive factors in the educational process.

In pedagogical and psychological research, the same thing is noted that ICT greatly affects the development of theoretical, creative and reflexive thinking of students. The figurative expression of this or that phenomenon, process in the memory of the student enriches the educational material and contributes to its scientific assimilation.

The main goal of the introduction of information and communication technologies into the educational process is precisely the emergence of new types of educational activities characteristic of the modern information environment.

It is known that primary education is considered the foundation of the system, the quality of teaching students will depend on it, and the primary school teacher will have a great responsibility. In our activities, we are introducing information technologies into the educational process, using them and collecting certain experience in the use of ICT in the educational process.

In cases of didactic correct application of ICT within the framework of a traditional lesson, it allows students to use information resources, increases the efficiency of independent work, gives new opportunities in general for the acquisition and strengthening of creativity, skills and abilities, allows the implementation of new forms and techniques of Education.

When ICT is used, it becomes easy to implement a personality-oriented approach in education, it became possible to effectively organize the entire educational process. In the course of the lesson, multimedia educational programs and presentations, projects were created using ready-made multimedia products and computer education software, internet networking tools in educational and extracurricular activities. Information technology can be applied in all academic disciplines. The use of educational and Game programs in classes gives a great effect. In the lessons of the native language, exercises to improve literacy will help, in which children perform various practical tasks on computers. Using a set of various didactic materials for students of elementary grades, it is possible to prepare mixed computer programs in which visual exercises, control exercises and test test modules are included. Three for him current study and generalized repetition of the rules on science

The 1st grade reading lesson can be used by preparing electronic tutorials. In it, it is possible to give a sound-letter analysis of the word, the structure of the syllables of the word, the study of some orthograms, various interesting visual and sound material. Bright pictures, unusual, interesting assignments will help to increase interest in the native language in younger students, allow you to get acquainted with the educational material in the form of a game, provide ample opportunities for self-control and educational reflection.

It can be used in mathematics lessons by preparing programs for 'gaming issues'. Various materials on many topics are given to what is studied in the elementary grade. Tasks of different levels of complexity help to develop the perception and creative abilities of each student. The use of computer animated slides in solving problems increases the interest of the lesson. It is possible to return to the beginning of the matter at any time when the dominant sides of UAR want, consisting in the fact that in its individual parts it is possible to stop, talk with readers, listen to their thoughts. In elementary classes, it is possible to apply slides with animated exercises to the movement. To create such slides, animated paintings taken from the internet can be used.

It is necessary to use test tasks in all academic disciplines. Since the tests were initially used only in printed form, now it is possible to dial them on a computer and deal with each reader. During the years of use of ICT, it is possible to prepare a series of different tests from Grade 1 to Grade 3 in mathematics, artistic Reading, native language, almost all subjects and other academic subjects. Now it is necessary to use computer tests in classes, and not only in printed form. They allow, as soon as they are completed, to immediately receive an assessment, the assessment is presented by the computer itself, allowing them to identify their shortcomings on one or another topic.

Development of computer tests on all subjects of the discipline' Natural Science "mumikin. For example: 'our land is water bodies', 'Mother Earth', 'Forest and fields are the wealth of nature', 'agricultural fields', 'our land', 'underground resources', 'the territorial structure of our country', 'local livestock and plants', etc. The word studied in the native language presents difficulties in interpreting its lexical content and dividing units into types. These are: antonyms, synonyms, homonyms. Through tests, the lexical capabilities of students develop, teach to find the correct and portable meaning of a word, to correctly select synonyms, to distinguish Synonyms, Antonyms and homonyms. The use of the 'reverse game' test, dedicated to working with antonyms, effectively affects the explanation of the lesson to students.

The main thing: the eyes, brain and hands of the student are involved in the implementation of the test tasks, while the elements of the game will be important in developing interest in the work they are doing and, consequently, ensuring the desired

level of intensity of the educational process. In addition to tests, crasswords, schemes, tables are used, students work directly at the computer in the independent study of lesson materials.

Presentations created using Microsoft Power Point programs are a very effective form of using ICT in the learning process. In the presentation-the main thing is informativeness, exhibitionism, curiosity. Through the Maskur program, it is possible to use Photos, Pictures, Animation, additional information when creating presentations on various topics and disciplines.

Information and communication technologies expand the capabilities of the teacher in bringing students into an interesting world, in which students independently search, receive, analyze and convey information to others. Teaching a child to work with information, to study is an important task of modern primary classes. Primary classes are formed only the main directions of use of ICT in the educational process. The widespread use of ICT in the organization of extracurricular activities of students will primarily consist in the preparation of various reports, conducting extracurricular activities, etc.

For the use of Information Communication Technologies in the educational process, there must be certain conditions, that is, information resources computer video projector, multimedia tools, printer, scanner, as well as modern software tools. Today, the main component of computer and information technology tools in improving the effectiveness of the educational process: educational programs, multimedia technologies, educational methodological support of distance learning, virtual labaratoria, electronic textbook (ED), electronic educational library, international internet systems, etc.will be of paramount importance and importance.

The effectiveness and excellence of the educational process will depend on how the information is given to the knowledge recipient, how it is perceived by them and how they are applied to the practice. Multimedia technologies describe each information about the pedagogical and economic processes under study to the pupils in action, voice and video views. This, while saving the time it takes to provide large amounts of information, increases the level of their acceptance and practical use of new information. In other words, a number of foreign researchers who have studied the importance of computer and Information Technology in the educational process in the education and training of the younger generation believe that in the process of transition to a new information stage of the development of society, the rational use of technical means in the younger generation, the reception, processing and use of

Also, the researchers emphasize the need to form the psychological preparation of children for the information environment from the early school period. This requires downloading qualitatively new requirements for primary education, which is

considered the first stage of school education, and increasing the computer literacy of children in it. After all, new information technologies, in combination with traditional means of education, make it possible to raise a child as a creative person.

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